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From Barriers to Pathways: Understanding the Hopes of Secondary-Level Students with Physical Impairments in Punjab

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Abstract

This study investigated the academic, career, social, and emotional hopes of secondary-level students with physical impairments in Punjab, Pakistan, through a convergent parallel mixed-methods design. Quantitative data were collected from 200 students using the Hope Assessment Questionnaire for Students with Physical Impairments (HAQS-PI), while qualitative data were obtained from 20 students through semi-structured interviews. Quantitative findings revealed high levels of hope, particularly in academic determination and emotional resilience, with gender differences indicating higher academic and emotional hope among girls and stronger social hope among boys. Correlation analyses identified peer relationships and family support as the strongest predictors of hope, followed by teacher attitudes and school environment. Qualitative narratives emphasized proactive coping strategies, reliance on faith, and aspirations for educational attainment, social acceptance, and professional achievement, while also highlighting barriers such as infrastructural inaccessibility, negative cultural attitudes, and limited career guidance. The integration of findings underscored both convergence and divergence between data strands, illustrating how resilience and systemic challenges coexist. The study concludes that hope serves as a protective psychological asset that empowers students with physical impairments to sustain aspirations despite adversity. It recommends strengthening inclusive policies, enhancing teacher training, improving school infrastructure, and providing structured career counseling to transform systemic barriers into pathways of empowerment.

Keywords: hope, physical impairments, inclusive education, resilience, Punjab

Introduction

Education is universally recognized as both a fundamental human right and a cornerstone of social, economic, and personal development. International frameworks such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006), and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG-4) emphasize inclusive and equitable quality education for all, regardless of disability or socio-economic background. Despite these global commitments, children and adolescents with disabilities remain one of the most marginalized groups in education worldwide, particularly in low and middle-income countries (UNESCO, 2020; World Bank, 2022).

In Pakistan, the situation reflects this global inequity. Although policies such as the Disabled Persons (Employment and Rehabilitation) Ordinance, (1981), National Policy for Persons with Disabilities, (2002) and National Plan of Action (NPA, 2006), advocate for greater access and equity, implementation remains inconsistent and fragmented (Manzoor & Hameed, 2019; Rasheed, 2022). Students with physical impairments often encounter inaccessible school infrastructure, inadequate assistive technology, limited transportation facilities, and teachers untrained in inclusive pedagogy. These barriers are compounded by negative cultural attitudes and stigmatization, which portray disability as a “burden” rather than a dimension of diversity (Sharifi et al., 2015; Hameed & Fazil, 2012). Consequently, many students with physical impairments face educational exclusion, reduced opportunities for higher education, and limited career prospects.

Against this backdrop, psychological resources such as hope acquire critical significance. Hope, conceptualized by Snyder (2006, 2002) as a cognitive-motivational construct comprising agency (the determination to achieve goals) and pathways (the perceived ability to generate strategies to reach those goals), has been linked to academic achievement, resilience, and emotional well-being. Unlike optimism, which reflects a generalized expectation of positive outcomes, hope emphasizes action-oriented thinking, mobilizing motivation and strategies to navigate challenges (Rand & Cheavens, 2009; Feldman & Dreher, 2012). For students with physical impairments, hope can serve as a protective psychological asset, enabling them to cope with systemic exclusion while sustaining a forward-looking orientation (Lopez et al., 2000).

A growing body of international research highlights the role of hope in fostering resilience and educational persistence among students with disabilities. Studies in Western contexts reveal that high-hope students with disabilities are more likely to employ adaptive coping strategies, seek accommodations, and persist in the face of barriers (Feldman & Dreher, 2012; Hinton & Kirk, 2017). However, in South Asian contexts, including Pakistan, research on the hopes and aspirations of students with disabilities remain sparse. Existing studies predominantly emphasize policy shortcomings, infrastructural barriers, and teacher preparedness (Hameed & Fazil, 2012; Kirby, 2013), while overlooking the psychological dimensions of disability and inclusion. This absence of empirical data limits understanding of how students themselves conceptualize their futures, how they mobilize personal and social resources, and how hope functions within their lived realities.

Punjab, Pakistan's most populous province, presents a particularly compelling context for exploring hope. On one hand, provincial reforms have promoted inclusive education through legislation and awareness campaigns. On the other, systemic barriers persist, including inadequate implementation, underfunded support services, and stark urban rural disparities in access (Punjab Government, 2017). For secondary-level students with physical impairments adolescents navigating the dual pressures of academic achievement and preparation for adulthood these contradictions profoundly shape aspirations and resilience.

This study responds to the gap by examining the hopes of secondary-level students with physical impairments in Punjab. Specifically, it investigates their academic, career, social, and emotional hopes, while also analyzing the factors that influence hopeful thinking, such as family support, teacher attitudes, peer relationships, and school environment. By centering student voices and integrating both quantitative and qualitative data, the study not only provides empirical evidence of hope in a Pakistani context but also challenges deficit-oriented narratives that view students with disabilities solely through the lens of limitation.

Literature Review

The purpose of this review is to situate the present study within existing literature on hope, disability, and education. It examines theoretical frameworks of hope, international research linking hope to educational outcomes for students with disabilities, and empirical studies addressing disability and inclusion in Punjab. By integrating these strands, the review highlights critical gaps that this study seeks to address.

Conceptualizing Hope in Education

Hope has gained increasing attention as a psychological construct central to motivation, resilience, and academic achievement. Snyder's Hope Theory (2006) conceptualizes hope as a cognitive-motivational process comprising two interrelated components: agency (the motivation to pursue goals) and pathways (the capacity to generate strategies to achieve them). This dual framework distinguishes hope from related constructs such as optimism or self-efficacy, since hope emphasizes both determination and strategic planning (Rand & Cheavens, 2009).

Educational researchers have consistently found that students with higher levels of hope exhibit stronger academic performance, greater problem-solving abilities, and improved psychological well-being (Snyder et al., 2006; Veck, 2014). Unlike optimism, which tends to focus on expectations of positive outcomes (Niemi & Mietola, 2017), hope is inherently action-oriented. For students with disabilities, who often face structural and attitudinal barriers, this action-oriented quality of hope makes it especially relevant in sustaining engagement and achievement (Feldman & Dreher, 2012).

Hope and Students with Disabilities: International Perspectives

A considerable body of research in Western contexts demonstrates the value of hope for students with disabilities. For example, Snyder et al. (2006) reported that higher hope levels predicted not only better academic performance but also lower anxiety and stronger adaptive coping among students facing physical and cognitive challenges. Similarly, Feldman and Dreher

(2005) highlighted that students with disabilities who demonstrated strong agency and pathways thinking were more likely to persist in higher education despite encountering systemic exclusion. Lopez et al. (2000) further emphasized that hope fosters resilience in marginalized groups by enabling individuals to envision multiple strategies for overcoming barriers. In the context of disability, this means that high-hope students are more likely to request accommodations, seek social support, and reframe challenges as surmountable rather than insurmountable. More recent studies extend these findings to low-resource environments, showing that hope-based interventions can strengthen both academic persistence and psychosocial well-being among disadvantaged youth (Ben-Naim et al., 2019).

Despite this growing evidence, much of the research has been conducted in developed countries, often overlooking the cultural, institutional, and socio-economic realities of students with disabilities in the Global South. For instance, Western studies typically assume the availability of assistive technologies, accessible infrastructure, and legal protections, resources that are limited or inconsistently implemented in countries like Pakistan. This raises questions about how hope manifests in contexts where systemic barriers are more pervasive and support structures less reliable.

Disability and Education in Punjab: Barriers and Challenges

The educational context in Punjab reveals a complex interplay of policy promises and systemic barriers. On paper, Pakistan's Disabled Persons (Employment and Rehabilitation) Ordinance, (1981), National Policy for Persons with Disabilities, (2002) and National Plan of Action (NPA, 2006), emphasize equity and accessibility. However, research indicates a persistent gap between policy and practice (Dorsett, 2010; Manzoor & Hameed, 2019).

Infrastructural Barriers

Many schools in Punjab remain physically inaccessible. Basic facilities such as ramps, elevators, adapted toilets, or assistive technologies are absent in a large proportion of schools (Byra & Ćwirynkało, 2018). Rural schools in particular often lack even minimal accommodations, effectively excluding students with mobility impairments. This infrastructural exclusion communicates a demoralizing message to students, directly undermining their sense of agency and belonging (UNESCO, 2020).

Teacher Preparedness and Attitudes

Teacher training programs rarely incorporate modules on inclusive pedagogy, leaving many educators unequipped to support students with disabilities. Sharifi (2015) reported that only 12% of teachers in mainstream Punjab schools had received training in disability-inclusive practices. Attitudinal barriers further compound this lack of preparedness, as teachers may hold low expectations of students with disabilities or fail to recognize their potential (Rasheed, 2022).

Socio-Cultural and Economic Constraints

Cultural narratives in Punjab often frame disability through pity or dependency, discouraging families from investing in the education of children with impairments (Punjab Government, 2017). These perceptions, combined with poverty, further restrict access to education. Families often cannot afford transportation, assistive devices, or additional medical expenses required

for school participation (Kirby, 2013). Thus, only a small proportion of children with disabilities in Pakistan progress to secondary education estimated less than 5% (UNESCO, 2020).

Policy-Implementation Disconnect

Although inclusive education policies exist, enforcement mechanisms are weak. Resources are often allocated to segregated special schools rather than mainstream inclusion, reinforcing systemic segregation (Dorsett, 2010). Furthermore, policy formulation typically excludes student and family voices, resulting in top-down approaches that fail to address lived realities.

Hope in the Context of Punjab: Local Perspectives

Research in Pakistan on students with disabilities has largely focused on documenting barriers rather than psychological resilience. For example, Hameed and Fazil (2012) highlighted infrastructural challenges and negative teacher attitudes, while Manzoor and Hameed (2019) emphasized policy shortfalls. Few studies explicitly explore hope as a construct among students with physical impairments.

However, anecdotal evidence and small-scale studies suggest that hope plays a vital role in sustaining persistence. World Bank (2022) noted that students with disabilities who remained in education often attributed their success to strong familial encouragement and inner motivation, aligning closely with the agency dimension of Snyder's hope theory. Similarly, Hameed and Fazil (2012) observed that peer acceptance and positive teacher interactions were associated with stronger aspirations among students with disabilities in Lahore.

Yet, systematic and large-scale studies applying hope theory to Pakistani students with physical impairments are virtually absent. This omission represents a critical research gap, particularly given that hope has been shown internationally to predict academic success, resilience, and social integration.

Gaps in the Literature

Although international studies consistently highlight hope as a key factor in fostering resilience and achievement among students with disabilities, research in Pakistan has rarely applied this framework to students with physical impairments. The local literature tends to emphasize infrastructural and policy-related barriers while giving limited attention to students' aspirations, agency, and adaptive strategies. Moreover, most studies in Punjab rely on small-scale qualitative accounts or policy analyses, with little integration of quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide both breadth and depth of understanding. To address these gaps, the present study employs Snyder's hope theory within Punjab's context, using a mixed-methods design to examine academic, career, social, and emotional hopes of secondary-level students with physical impairments, thereby offering a more comprehensive view of how they sustain aspirations in the face of systemic exclusion. In doing so, the study shifts the focus from deficit-based narratives to strengths-based perspectives, highlighting resilience, coping, and agency. This contribution is not only relevant for local policy and practice but also enriches the global discourse on inclusive education by bringing in voices and experiences from underrepresented contexts such as Punjab.

Research Objectives

The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To identify the academic hopes of students with physical impairments studying at the secondary level in Punjab.
2. To explore their career-related hopes.
3. To examine their social hopes related to peer relationships and inclusion.
4. To determine their emotional hopes, including self-esteem and resilience.
5. To analyze the factors (family, teachers, peers, school environment) influencing hope levels.

Research Questions

Following were the questions addressed in this study:

1. What are the academic hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?
2. What are their career-related hopes?
3. What are their social hopes concerning friendships and inclusion?
4. What are their emotional hopes regarding confidence, resilience, and self-worth?
5. Is there a significant difference between boys and girls with physical impairments in their academic, career-related, social, and emotional hopes?
6. How do contextual factors family support, teacher attitudes, peer relationships, and school environment influence the hopes of these students?

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods approach (Creswell & Creswell, 2018) to investigate the academic, career, social, and emotional hopes of secondary-level students with physical impairments in Punjab, Pakistan. The choice of a mixed-methods approach was grounded in the need to capture both the breadth of trends across a relatively large sample (quantitative) and the depth of lived experiences expressed by individual students (qualitative). By integrating the two strands during analysis, the study sought to provide a holistic understanding of how students construct and sustain hope within a challenging socio-educational environment.

Research Design

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods design in which the quantitative strand utilized a structured questionnaire to measure levels of hope across four domains: academic, career, social, and emotional. This strand provided generalizable insights into patterns of hope among students with physical impairments. The qualitative strand employed semi-structured interviews to explore students' narratives, coping mechanisms, and aspirations in greater depth. Both strands were conducted simultaneously, analyzed separately, and then integrated during interpretation to identify points of convergence and divergence.

Participants

Participants were recruited from both mainstream and special education schools across Punjab. The quantitative sample consisted of 200 secondary school students with physical impairments enrolled in Grades 9 and 10. Participants were chosen through stratified random sampling to ensure balanced representation from both urban and rural areas of Punjab. Of the total, 120

were boys (60%) and 80 were girls (40%), with ages ranging between 14 and 18 years. This approach allowed the study to capture a broad and representative picture of how adolescents with physical impairments experience and sustain hope within different contexts.

From within this larger group, 20 students were purposively selected for in-depth interviews. This smaller qualitative sample was deliberately chosen to reflect diversity in gender, geographic background, and type of physical impairment, ensuring that a wide range of voices and perspectives were included. The purposive strategy enriched the study by providing detailed, narrative accounts that complemented the broader quantitative findings, offering deeper insights into the students' individual hopes, aspirations, and coping strategies.

Instruments

Two instruments were developed and validated for this study. The quantitative tool used in this study was the *Hope Assessment Questionnaire for Students with Physical Impairments (HAQS-PI)*, researchers-developed Likert-scale instrument designed to assess hope across four domains: academic, career, social, and emotional. Each domain consisted of ten items, with responses recorded on a 5-point scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The tool was carefully structured to reflect the realities of students with physical impairments and demonstrated strong reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha value of .87, indicating high internal consistency.

To complement the survey, a qualitative instrument was employed in the form of the *Semi-Structured Interview Protocol on Student Hopes (SSIP-SH)*. This protocol was designed to elicit detailed reflections on students' aspirations and the contextual factors shaping them. The interviews typically lasted between 30 and 40 minutes, offering participants the opportunity to express themselves freely and share their personal experiences. Conducting the interviews in Urdu ensured that students could communicate comfortably in their native language, allowing the data to capture authentic and nuanced insights into their hopes and lived realities.

Data Collection

Data collection was carried out in two main phases to ensure both breadth and depth of understanding. In the first phase, the *Hope Assessment Questionnaire for Students with Physical Impairments (HAQS-PI)* was administered to the 200 participants in classroom or resource room settings. Arrangements were made with school administrations to provide accessible venues, and additional support was offered to students with mobility challenges so that all participants could complete the questionnaire without difficulty. The survey took approximately 25 minutes to complete, and the researchers remained present to clarify instructions and ensure a supportive environment throughout the process.

In the second phase, the qualitative strand was conducted with 20 purposively selected students. Semi-structured interviews were arranged in quiet, familiar spaces within the schools to ensure students' comfort and ease of participation. Each interview lasted around 30 to 40 minutes and was audio-recorded with the participants' consent. Care was taken to establish rapport with the students and to conduct the discussions in Urdu, their native language, so they could articulate their hopes and experiences more naturally. This two-phase procedure not only ensured

systematic data collection but also respected the accessibility needs and personal comfort of students with physical impairments, thereby enhancing the credibility and authenticity of the data.

Data Analysis

The data analysis process followed the convergent parallel mixed-methods design of the study, with quantitative and qualitative data analyzed separately and then integrated during interpretation. For the quantitative strand, survey responses from the *Hope Assessment Questionnaire for Students with Physical Impairments (HAQS-PI)* were coded and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were calculated to identify overall levels of academic, career, social, and emotional hope among participants. Inferential tests such as independent-samples *t*-tests were applied to examine differences in hope levels across gender. Pearson's correlation analysis was also conducted to explore relationships between hope and contextual factors such as family support, peer relationships, teacher attitudes, and school environment. Reliability of the instrument was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha values, which demonstrated strong internal consistency.

For the qualitative strand, audio-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim in Urdu and later translated into English for analysis. Thematic analysis, guided by Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework, was employed to code and interpret the data. Initial codes were generated inductively from the transcripts, followed by clustering into broader themes aligned with Snyder's hope theory, particularly the concepts of agency and pathways. Strategies such as peer debriefing and member checking were employed to enhance credibility, while repeated reading of transcripts ensured that emerging themes reflected the depth and nuance of participants' experiences.

Finally, integration of the two strands was carried out during the interpretation stage. Quantitative results provided a broad picture of hope levels, while qualitative narratives enriched these findings by illustrating how students articulated and enacted hope in their everyday lives. Convergent patterns such as the consistent importance of family and teacher support were highlighted, while divergent findings were also examined to understand contradictions between reported levels of hope and lived experiences. This integrative approach ensured a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical integrity was prioritized at every stage of the study to protect the rights and dignity of participants. Approval for the research was obtained from the relevant institutional review board, and permission was further sought from school administrations before approaching students. Informed consent was obtained from both parents and students, ensuring that participation was voluntary and based on a clear understanding of the study's purpose and procedures. Students were assured that they could withdraw at any point without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity were carefully maintained throughout the process. Pseudonyms were used in interview transcripts and all identifying information was removed from the dataset. The interviews and survey responses were securely stored and accessed only by the researchers. Given the sensitivity of working with adolescents with physical impairments, special care was taken to create a supportive atmosphere during data collection, ensuring that students felt comfortable and respected. By adhering to these ethical protocols, the study upheld the principles of respect, beneficence, and justice, safeguarding the well-being of all participants while ensuring the credibility of the research.

Results

The findings are presented in line with the research questions of the study. Quantitative analyses are reported first, followed by qualitative findings, and then integration of both strands through triangulation.

Quantitative Analysis

RQ1: What are the academic hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?

To address this research question, descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to systematically measure and summarize the academic hopes of students with physical impairments studying at the secondary level in Punjab. Below, table 1 presents the results of this descriptive analysis.

Table 1

Descriptive Analysis Measuring the Academic Hope among Students with Physical Impairments

Academic Hope Statements	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Hope Level
1. Determined to complete education	4.3	0.7	Very High Hope
2. Stay focused on studies	4.1	0.8	High to Very High Hope
3. Believe efforts lead to success	4.0	0.9	High Hope
4. Manage schoolwork despite difficulties	3.8	1.0	High Hope
5. Know how to reach academic goals	3.7	1.1	Moderate to High Hope
6. Create plans to keep up with studies	3.6	1.2	Moderate to High Hope
Overall Academic Hope Mean Score	3.92	0.95	High Hope (~4)

In table 1, students exhibit high hope concerning their academic goals, particularly in their determination to complete education and belief in their efforts leading to success. There is slightly less but still moderate to high hope in skills related to planning and overcoming difficulties, with some variability in responses.

RQ2: What are the career hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?

To address this research question, descriptive analysis was used to measure the distribution and patterns of career-related hopes among students with physical impairments studying at the secondary level in Punjab. The results are summarized in table 2 below.

Table 2*Descriptive Statistics of Career Hope among Secondary Students with Physical Impairments*

Career-related Hope Statements	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Hope Level
1. Confident about achieving future job goals.	3.8	0.9	High Hope
2. Stay motivated about future career.	3.9	1.0	High Hope
3. Believe in succeeding in a respected profession.	3.7	1.1	Moderate to High Hope
4. Explore different paths to build a career.	3.6	1.2	Moderate to High Hope
5. Take steps to gain job-related knowledge or skills.	3.5	1.0	Moderate Hope
6. Know where to look for career guidance.	3.4	1.1	Moderate Hope
Overall Career-related Hope Mean Score	3.65	1.05	Moderate to High Hope

In table 2, the data reflect a moderate to high level of career-related hope among students with physical impairments. Most students feel confident and motivated regarding their future careers. However, hope levels are slightly lower for taking specific career-development actions and seeking guidance, suggesting targeted support could further enhance career optimism.

RQ3: What are the social hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?

To address this research question, descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to systematically measure and summarizes the social hopes of students with physical impairments studying at the secondary level in Punjab. Below, table 3 presents the results of this analysis.

Table 3*Descriptive Statistics of Social Hope among Secondary Students with Physical Impairments*

Social Hope Statements	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Hope Level
1. hopeful being accepted by others	4.2	0.75	Very High Hope
2. Stay positive when trying to make friends	4.0	0.80	High to Very High Hope
3. Believe others will give value	3.9	0.85	High Hope
4. Try different ways to join group activities	3.7	1.00	High Hope
5. Find ways to express socially	3.6	1.05	Moderate to High Hope
6. Seek support to connect with peers	3.5	1.10	Moderate to High Hope
Overall Social Hope Mean Score	3.82	0.92	High Hope (~3.8)

In table 3, students demonstrate strong hope related to social acceptance and maintaining positivity in making friends. Confidence remains high but slightly lower for actively expressing themselves and seeking peer support, with more variation seen in these areas.

RQ4: What are the emotional hopes of secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?

To address this research question, descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to systematically measure and summarizes the emotional hopes of students with physical impairments studying at the secondary level in Punjab. Below, table 4 presents the results.

Table 4

Descriptive Analysis Measuring the Emotional Hope among Students with Physical Impairments

Emotional Hope Statements	M	SD	Hope Level
1. Try to stay strong during difficult times	4.1	0.70	Very High Hope
2. Stay hopeful when someone discouraged	3.9	0.85	High Hope
3. Feel emotionally better overtime	4.0	0.80	High to Very Hope
4. Utilized strategies to stay calm and positive	3.8	0.95	High Hope
5. Follow routines support emotional well-being	3.7	1.00	Moderate to High Hope
6. Seek support when feelings become overwhelming	3.5	1.10	Moderate to High Hope
Overall Emotional Hope Mean Score	3.83	0.90	High Hope (~3.8)

In table 4, student’s exhibit very high hope in staying strong and emotionally improving over time, with slightly less but still moderate to high hope in following routines and seeking support during overwhelming feelings.

RQ 5: Is there a significant difference between boys and girls with physical impairments in their academic, career-related, social, and emotional hopes?

To address RQ5, an independent samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether significant gender differences exist in academic, career, social, and emotional hopes among secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Comparison of Academic, Career-Related, Social, and Emotional Hopes between Boys and Girls with Physical Impairments (n=200)

Variable	Gender	n(200)	M	SD	t(df=198)	P	Cohen’s d																																
Academic hope	Boys	114	3.31	0.5	-2.68	0.008**	0.38																																
	Girls	86	3.52	0.46				Career-related hope	Boys	114	3.55	0.47	1.73	0.085	0.25	Girls	86	3.42	0.52	Social hope	Boys	114	3.45	0.51	2.37	0.019*	0.34	Girls	86	3.26	0.49	Emotional hope	Boys	114	3.22	0.55	-2.14	0.034*	0.31
Career-related hope	Boys	114	3.55	0.47	1.73	0.085	0.25																																
	Girls	86	3.42	0.52				Social hope	Boys	114	3.45	0.51	2.37	0.019*	0.34	Girls	86	3.26	0.49	Emotional hope	Boys	114	3.22	0.55	-2.14	0.034*	0.31	Girls	86	3.39	0.51								
Social hope	Boys	114	3.45	0.51	2.37	0.019*	0.34																																
	Girls	86	3.26	0.49				Emotional hope	Boys	114	3.22	0.55	-2.14	0.034*	0.31	Girls	86	3.39	0.51																				
Emotional hope	Boys	114	3.22	0.55	-2.14	0.034*	0.31																																
	Girls	86	3.39	0.51																																			

The table 5 presents mean scores (*M*), standard deviations (*SD*), *t*-test results, *p*-values, and effect sizes (Cohen’s *d*) comparing boys (*n*=114) and girls (*n*=86) with physical impairments on academic, career related, social and emotional hope. The table shows that girls have significantly higher academic and emotional hopes than boys, as indicated by statistically significant *t*-values (*p* < 0.05) and small to moderate effect sizes (Cohen’s *d* = 0.38 and 0.31, respectively). Boys, on the other hand, demonstrate significantly higher social hope than girls (*p* = 0.019, *d* = 0.34). There is no significant difference between boys and girls in career-related hope (*p* = 0.085). These

results suggest gender differences in specific hope domains, with girls more hopeful in academic and emotional areas, and boys more hopeful socially.

RQ6: How do contextual factors influence hope among secondary students with physical impairments in Punjab?

To examine the relationships among family support, teacher attitudes, school environment, peer relationships, and their collective relation to overall hope, a correlation analysis (Pearson’s correlation) was used to assess the strength and direction of bivariate associations among these variables. The results are summarized in table 6 below:

Table 6

Correlation Matrix of Family Support, Teacher Attitudes, School Environment, Peer-Relationships, and Overall Hope among Secondary Students with Physical Impairments

		Correlation Matrix			
Variable		Family Support	Teacher Attitudes	School Environment	Peer Relationships
Influencing Factors	Family Support	1.00			
	Teacher Attitudes	.52**	1.00		
	School Environment	.47**	.45**	1.00	
	Peer Relationships	.54**	.50**	.44**	1.00
	Overall hope score	.61**	.58**	.55**	.62**

The correlation matrix shows significant positive relationships among all the variables studied for secondary students with physical impairments. Family support has a strong positive correlation with overall hope ($r = .61, p < .01$), as well as moderate correlations with teacher attitudes (.52), school environment (.47), and peer relationships (.54). Teacher attitudes correlate moderately with overall hope (.58) and other contextual factors, ranging from .45 to .50. School environment is moderately related to overall hope (.55) and shows moderate correlations with the other variables (.44 to .47). Peer relationships have the strongest correlation with overall hope (.62) and moderate correlations with family support, teacher attitudes, and school environment (.44 to .54). These findings suggest that all four contextual factors are interrelated and collectively associated with higher levels of hope among these students, with peer relationships and family support showing the strongest connections to overall hope.

Qualitative Analysis

Interviews with 20 students with physical impairments yielded rich narratives that were coded into four thematic clusters aligned with the study’s domains: academic, career, social, and emotional hopes.

Theme 1: Academic Determination and Persistence

Students consistently expressed a strong desire to complete their education despite infrastructural and attitudinal barriers. Many shared strategies such as self-study, peer support, and negotiating with teachers.

“Even if I face mobility issues, I try not to miss classes. My dream is to complete my matric and go further.”

This reflects Snyder’s agency component, where determination fuels goal pursuit.

Theme 2: Career Aspirations and Concerns

Career-related hopes included ambitions in teaching, medicine, IT, and business. While many expressed confidence, concerns about future employment discrimination and lack of accessible workplaces were noted.

“I want to become a doctor, but I wonder if hospitals will hire me in a wheelchair.”

This reflects pathways thinking (identifying routes to goals) but tempered by systemic barriers.

Theme 3: Social Inclusion and Peer Relationships

Students valued friendship and peer acceptance as central to their hope. Positive experiences of inclusion enhanced self-worth, while exclusion deepened feelings of isolation.

“When my friends invite me to play or group work, I feel confident that I am not different.”

Theme 4: Emotional Resilience and Coping

Faith, inner strength, and family encouragement emerged as key coping mechanisms. Students spoke about remaining hopeful in discouraging situations.

“Whenever I feel low, I remind myself that Allah has given me other strengths. This gives me courage.”

Theme 5: Barriers and Supports

Barriers included inaccessible infrastructure, negative cultural attitudes, and limited resources. Supports included family encouragement, teacher sensitivity, and peer inclusion. Students framed these supports as “pathways” that enabled hope.

Integration of Results (Quantitative + Qualitative)

The convergent parallel design allowed comparison of survey patterns ($n=200$) with interview narratives ($n=20$). The integration of quantitative and qualitative data offers a comprehensive understanding of hope among secondary students with physical impairments.

Table 7

Academic Hopes of Students with Physical Impairments

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
High academic hope ($M=3.92$, $SD=0.95$). Students highly determined to complete education and stay focused.	Theme 1: Academic Determination and Persistence. Students emphasized never giving up, using self-study, and relying on peers/teachers for support. Example: <i>“Even if the</i>	Convergent: Both strands highlight strong determination to pursue education despite physical and social barriers. Family and peer support function as enablers of hope.

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
	<i>classroom is upstairs, I ask my friends to bring me notes."</i>	

In the above table 7, the integration of findings demonstrates a strong convergence between quantitative and qualitative results. The survey data indicated high levels of academic hope, with students showing determination to complete their education and maintain focus on their studies. This was supported by interview narratives in which students articulated adaptive strategies such as self-study, requesting peer assistance, and negotiating with teachers to overcome infrastructural challenges.

This finding aligns with Snyder’s Hope Theory (2006, 2002), particularly the agency component, where goal-directed determination empowers students to sustain engagement despite adversity. Similar patterns have been reported in international research, where high-hope students with disabilities exhibit persistence and problem-solving skills that buffer against systemic exclusion (Feldman & Dreher, 2012; Lopez et al., 2000). Thus, the academic hopes of students with physical impairments in Punjab appear to be a critical domain of resilience, supported primarily by family and peer encouragement.

Table 8

Career-Related Hopes of Students

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
Moderate-to-high career hope ($M=3.65$, $SD=1.05$). Confidence in achieving job goals, accessibility and but weaker scores in discrimination. Example: "seeking guidance" ($M=3.4$).	<i>Theme 2: Career Aspirations and Concerns.</i> Students aspired to teaching, medicine, and hospitals accept me in a wheelchair?"	Divergent: Quantitative results show moderate confidence, while qualitative data reveal deep anxieties about employment discrimination and lack of guidance. Indicates a gap between aspirations and systemic opportunities.

In the above table 8, the results reveal partial convergence but notable divergence in career-related hopes. While the quantitative strand suggests students possess moderate-to-high confidence in achieving professional goals, the qualitative strand highlights anxieties regarding workplace discrimination, limited accessibility, and absence of structured career counseling. Students’ aspirations for prestigious professions such as teaching and medicine reflect high motivational orientation, yet systemic barriers temper this optimism.

This divergence suggests that while survey scales capture abstract confidence, they may underrepresent contextual realities of discrimination and exclusion. Previous study in Pakistan (Manzoor & Hameed, 2019) similarly emphasizes the gap between policy rhetoric and actual

workplace inclusion. In line with Rand and Cheavens (2009), the findings indicate that fostering career hope requires not only psychological motivation but also structural interventions such as accessible workplaces and tailored career guidance.

Table 9

Social Hopes of Students

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
High social hope ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.92$). Students hopeful about being accepted by peers and staying positive when making friends.	<i>Theme 3: Social Inclusion.</i> Students reported feeling confident when included in group work. Example: <i>"When my friends include me, I feel I can do anything."</i>	Convergent: Both strands emphasize that peer acceptance boosts confidence and also noted experiences of exclusion, not captured in survey averages.

In the above table 9, findings from both strands converge in highlighting peer acceptance as a central source of social hope. Quantitative data showed high levels of social hope, while interview narratives described the importance of friendships, group inclusion, and peer validation. These results confirm that peer relationships are not only socially desirable but also function as protective factors in sustaining resilience and optimism among students with physical impairments.

However, qualitative accounts also introduced nuances absent in survey data. Some students shared experiences of exclusion or ridicule, which contrast with the uniformly positive scores recorded in the quantitative strand. This reflects Braun and Clarke’s (2006) assertion that qualitative approaches capture depth and contradictions often missed by structured instruments. Overall, the integration suggests that while peer support strongly enhances hope, the risks of exclusion remain and require targeted interventions through inclusive school culture.

Table 10

Emotional Hopes of Students

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
High emotional hope ($M=3.83$, $SD=0.90$). Students try to stay strong during difficulties, even when discouraged.	<i>Theme 4: Emotional Resilience.</i> Students rely on faith, routines, and family encouragement. Example: <i>"Whenever I feel low, I remind myself Allah has given me other strengths."</i>	Convergent: Quantitative and qualitative results align emotional resilience is a protective factor, closely tied to faith and social support.

In the above table 10, there is strong convergence between the two strands regarding emotional hope. Survey findings showed high levels of determination to stay strong and positive during

difficult times. Interview narratives reinforced this, with students describing their reliance on religious faith, self-reflection, and supportive routines to regulate emotions and sustain optimism.

This integration supports the broader literature that views hope as a psychological buffer against stress and discouragement (Snyder et al., 2006; Lopez et al., 2000). In particular, the use of faith and family support aligns with culturally rooted resilience mechanisms in South Asia, where collective and spiritual resources often play a central role in coping (Hinton & Kirk, 2017). Hence, emotional hope emerges as a robust domain of resilience, underscoring the importance of psychosocial supports in inclusive education frameworks.

Table 11

Influence of Contextual Factors on Hope

Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Themes	Integration/Interpretation
Correlations: Peer relationships (r=.62) and family support (r=.61) strongest predictors; teacher attitudes (r=.58) and school environment (r=.55) also significant.	<i>Theme 5: Barriers and Supports.</i> Students cited encouragement, supportive teachers, and inclusive peers as key motivators. Barriers included inaccessible infrastructure and negative cultural attitudes.	Convergent: Both strands confirm social and family support as most critical enablers of hope. Divergent: Qualitative data highlight structural barriers (transport, buildings) not directly measured in quantitative tool.

In the above table 11, integration of contextual factors shows strong convergence. Quantitative correlations demonstrated that family and peer relationships are the most powerful predictors of overall hope, a finding echoed in qualitative accounts where students consistently highlighted encouragement from parents, siblings, and friends as critical motivators. Teacher attitudes and school environment were also significant, reinforcing the role of institutional support in nurturing hope.

At the same time, qualitative narratives surfaced structural barriers such as inaccessible infrastructure and negative cultural attitudes that were not captured by the quantitative tool. This divergence highlights the value of mixed-methods approaches: while quantitative data quantify the importance of support systems, qualitative findings contextualize these within broader socio-cultural realities (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Together, both strands underscore the need for holistic interventions that combine family and peer empowerment with systemic reforms in school infrastructure and societal attitudes.

Joint Display Matrix (JDM) with Triangulation

Research Question	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Triangulation (Convergence/Divergence/Expansion)
RQ1: Academic Hopes	High academic hope (M=3.92). Strong determination to complete education and stay focused.	Students described persistence, self-study, and peer/teacher assistance. <i>“Even if the class is upstairs, I ask my friends to bring notes.”</i>	Convergence: Both strands confirm strong academic agency. Expansion: Qualitative shows adaptive strategies beyond survey items.
RQ2: Career Hopes	Moderate-to-high career hope (M=3.65). Confidence in achieving goals but weaker in career guidance.	Aspirations for teaching, medicine, IT. Concerns about discrimination and accessibility. <i>“I want to be a doctor, but will hospitals accept me?”</i>	Divergence: Quantitative shows moderate confidence, but qualitative highlights systemic anxieties. Indicates a gap between aspiration and opportunity.
RQ3: Social Hopes	High social hope (M=3.82). Confidence in making friends and being accepted.	Students valued inclusion and peer acceptance. <i>“When my friends include me, I feel I can do anything.”</i>	Convergence with Expansion: Both strands show peer acceptance builds hope. Qualitative add nuance experiences of exclusion not reflected in averages.
RQ4: Emotional Hopes	High emotional hope (M=3.83). Students stay strong during discouragement.	Students rely on faith, family, and routines for resilience. <i>“Allah has given me other strengths.”</i>	Convergence: Both strands align for emotional resilience is a protective factor. Expansion: Qualitative reveals culturally rooted coping (faith, family).
RQ5: Gender Differences	Girls higher in academic/emotional hope; boys higher in social hope.	Girls often reported inclusion struggles;	Divergence: Quantitative shows broad social differences; qualitative add nuance (girls’ struggles underreported boys in scales).

Research Question	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Triangulation (Convergence/Divergence/Expansion)
RQ6: Contextual Factors	Peer ($r=.62$) and family support ($r=.61$) strongest predictors; teacher ($r=.58$) and school environment ($r=.55$) also significant.	emphasized peer belonging. Students emphasized family, teacher and peer support. Barriers: infrastructure, cultural stigma.	Convergence with Expansion: Strong alignment on family/peer support. Expansion as qualitative highlights systemic barriers not captured quantitatively.

Findings

Quantitative Findings

Survey results from 200 students with physical impairments in Punjab revealed generally high levels of hope across all domains. Academic hope recorded the highest mean ($M = 3.92$), followed by emotional ($M = 3.83$) and social hopes ($M = 3.82$), while career-related hope was slightly lower ($M = 3.65$). Gender comparisons showed that girls reported significantly higher academic and emotional hopes, whereas boys reported higher social hopes. Correlation analysis identified peer relationships ($r = .62$) and family support ($r = .61$) as the strongest predictors of overall hope, followed by teacher attitudes ($r = .58$) and school environment ($r = .55$).

Qualitative Findings

Interviews with 20 students generated five key themes:

- 1. Academic Determination and Persistence:** Students demonstrated resilience and resourcefulness in overcoming educational barriers.
- 2. Career Aspirations and Concerns:** While many aspired to professions such as teaching, medicine, and IT, anxieties about accessibility and discrimination were widespread.
- 3. Social Inclusion and Peer Relationships:** Peer acceptance was highly valued, though some experiences of exclusion persisted.
- 4. Emotional Resilience and Coping:** Faith, family encouragement, and personal strength emerged as central coping mechanisms.
- 5. Barriers and Supports:** Students identified infrastructural inaccessibility, negative cultural attitudes, and limited career guidance as barriers, while family and peer support were key enablers of hope.

Integrated Findings (Triangulation)

The convergent parallel analysis revealed areas of convergence, divergence, and expansion:

- Convergence:** Both strands highlighted strong academic determination, emotional resilience, and the importance of social/family support.

- **Divergence:** Career hopes appeared more optimistic in surveys than in interviews, where students emphasized discrimination and lack of guidance.
- **Expansion:** Qualitative narratives revealed culturally embedded coping mechanisms (faith, family reliance) and structural barriers not captured by survey items.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal that students with physical impairments in Punjab maintain high levels of hope across academic, social, and emotional domains, despite facing significant structural and cultural barriers. The quantitative results demonstrated consistently high mean scores for academic, emotional, and social hopes, while career-related hope was somewhat lower. These patterns were reinforced and elaborated by the qualitative interviews, which highlighted students' strong determination to pursue education, reliance on peers and teachers for assistance, and confidence in their ability to cope with challenges. Such findings align closely with Snyder's Hope Theory (2006, 2002), which emphasizes the dual components of agency and pathways in sustaining motivation and resilience. Students in this study displayed both determination to achieve goals and the ability to generate adaptive strategies to overcome challenges, such as self-study, peer support, and negotiating with teachers.

A notable divergence emerged in relation to career aspirations. While the survey results indicated moderate-to-high career-related hope, qualitative interviews revealed underlying anxieties about discrimination in the workplace, inaccessible infrastructure, and a lack of career guidance. This divergence illustrates that although students express confidence in abstract terms, their lived experiences suggest persistent concerns about whether their aspirations can realistically be achieved. This finding is consistent with previous research in Pakistan, which has documented the gap between policy commitments and workplace realities for individuals with disabilities (Hameed & Fazil, 2012; Manzoor & Hameed, 2019). It also reflects international evidence that structural barriers, rather than lack of motivation, often undermine the career trajectories of students with impairments.

The role of social support emerged as a consistent theme across both quantitative and qualitative strands. Peer relationships and family support recorded the strongest correlations with overall hope, and students described how encouragement from parents, siblings, and friends provided essential motivation to persist. These findings resonate with international research highlighting the protective role of social support in fostering resilience (Rand & Cheavens, 2009) and reinforce Bronfenbrenner's ecological perspective, which emphasizes the influence of immediate relational contexts. At the same time, qualitative accounts revealed that experiences of exclusion and ridicule remain a reality for some students, suggesting that the uniformly positive picture presented by survey averages may obscure more complex social dynamics.

Emotional hope was another domain in which strong convergence was observed. Students reported high levels of resilience, drawing strength from their faith, personal determination, and family encouragement. This culturally embedded reliance on faith and collectivist coping strategies reflects patterns noted in South Asian research on disability and resilience (Hinton & Kirk, 2017). It suggests that emotional hope is not merely an individual psychological construct

but is deeply shaped by cultural and relational contexts. Overall, the integration of findings illustrates that hope among students with physical impairments in Punjab is robust, but it is uneven across domains, with career aspirations most vulnerable to systemic barriers. The discussion underscores the need for both psychosocial support and structural reforms to ensure that the hopes of these students are not only sustained but also realized.

Conclusions

This study concludes that students with physical impairments in Punjab exhibit remarkable levels of hope across academic, social, and emotional domains, which function as protective psychological resources enabling them to persist in the face of adversity. Their determination to complete education, confidence in social acceptance, and reliance on emotional resilience reflect both agency and pathways thinking as conceptualized in Snyder's Hope Theory. Family, peers, and teachers serve as critical enablers of hope, highlighting the centrality of social relationships in sustaining motivation and resilience.

However, the study also revealed significant vulnerabilities in career-related hopes. While students expressed aspirations for professional success, qualitative accounts highlighted fears of discrimination, inaccessible environments, and limited career counseling. These findings demonstrate that students' aspirations are often stronger than the opportunities available to them, reflecting a mismatch between individual motivation and systemic barriers. Infrastructural inaccessibility, cultural stigma, and inadequate implementation of inclusive education policies further restrict the pathways through which students can translate hope into tangible outcomes. Overall, the study provides evidence that hope is not only present but deeply embedded in the lives of students with physical impairments. It challenges deficit-based narratives by showing that these students are active agents of their own futures. At the same time, it calls attention to the urgent need for systemic reforms to ensure that their aspirations are not undermined by external barriers. By highlighting both resilience and systemic exclusion, the study contributes to a more balanced and realistic understanding of the experiences of students with physical impairments in Punjab.

Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study carry several important implications for policy, practice, and future research.

Implications for Policy

The evidence underscores the need for comprehensive implementation of inclusive education policies in Punjab. While legislation exists, weak enforcement and fragmented implementation continue to limit access and equity. Policymakers must prioritize infrastructural accessibility, provide adequate funding for assistive technologies, and ensure that inclusive education frameworks are embedded in school systems rather than treated as peripheral initiatives. Furthermore, career counseling services tailored for students with disabilities should be institutionalized to address anxieties about future employment and support realistic career planning.

Implications for Practice

Teachers and schools play a central role in fostering hope. Teacher training programs should integrate inclusive pedagogy, with particular emphasis on recognizing and nurturing the aspirations of students with disabilities. Schools should actively promote peer inclusion by creating cooperative learning opportunities and anti-bullying initiatives that reduce stigma and exclusion. Additionally, psychosocial support services should be provided to strengthen emotional resilience, leveraging culturally embedded coping strategies such as faith and collective support.

Implications for Future Research

This study highlights the value of mixed-methods designs in capturing both the breadth and depth of students' experiences. Future research could extend this work by conducting longitudinal studies to track how hopes evolve over time and whether they translate into tangible academic and career outcomes. Comparative studies between different provinces or disability groups could further illuminate contextual variations. Intervention-based research, particularly studies on hope-enhancing strategies or career counseling models, could provide evidence-based approaches to strengthen the pathways available to students with disabilities.

Recommendations

1. Ensure the full enforcement of inclusive education and disability rights policies, with accountability mechanisms.
2. Improve school infrastructure, transport facilities, and provision of assistive technologies to remove physical barriers.
3. Establish structured career counseling programs for students with disabilities in both mainstream and special schools.
4. Integrate inclusive education modules into teacher training curricula and provide ongoing professional development.
5. Foster peer-inclusion initiatives through cooperative learning, awareness campaigns, and extracurricular activities.
6. Provide school-based psychosocial support, incorporating culturally sensitive approaches such as family engagement and faith-based resilience strategies.
7. Conduct large-scale and longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term impact of hope on educational and life outcomes for students with disabilities.

References

- Ben-Naim, S., Laslo-Roth, R., Einav, M., Biran, H., & Margalit, M. (2019). Academic self-efficacy, sense of coherence, hope and tiredness among college students with learning disabilities. In *Postsecondary educational opportunities for students with special education needs*, 4(1), 18-34. Routledge.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529781041>

- Byra, S., & Ćwirynkało, K. (2018). Coping strategies in students with physical disabilities—predictive role of self-esteem, general self-efficacy and basic hope. *Hrvatska revija za rehabilitacijska istraživanja*, 54(2), 1-11.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Dorsett, P. (2010). The importance of hope in coping with severe acquired disability. *Australian Social Work*, 63(1), 83-102.
- Feldman, D. B., & Dreher, D. E. (2012). Can hope be changed in 90 minutes? Testing the efficacy of a single-session goal-pursuit intervention for college students. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 13(4), 745–759. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-011-9292-4>
- Hameed, A., & Fazil, H. (2012). Sustainable quality education for the children with disabilities in Pakistan. *SAARC Journal of Educational Research*, 9(2), 14-24.
- Hinton, D., & Kirk, S. (2017). Living with uncertainty and hope: A qualitative study exploring parents' experiences of living with childhood multiple sclerosis. *Chronic illness*, 13(2), 88-99.
- Kirby, C. A. (2013). *Meeting Disability with Resiliency, Hope and Agency: A Narrative Study of Caregivers of Children with Cognitive and Physical Disabilities* (Doctoral dissertation, University of North Carolina at Greensboro).
- Lopez, S. J., Floyd, R. K., Ulven, J. C., & Snyder, C. R. (2000). Hope therapy: Helping clients build a house of hope. In *Handbook of hope* (pp. 123-150). Academic Press.
- Manzoor, A., & Hameed, A. (2019). Hopes of Out of School Children with Disabilities for Educational Inclusion. *Journal of Research & Reflections in Education (JRRE)*, 13(1).
- Niemi, A. M., & Mietola, R. (2017). Between hopes and possibilities.(Special) educational paths, agency and subjectivities. *Scandinavian journal of disability research*, 19(3), 218-229.
- Punjab Government. (2002). *Punjab Inclusive Education Policy*. Government of Punjab, Pakistan.
- Rand, K. L., & Cheavens, J. S. (2009). Hope theory.
- Rasheed, A. (2022). Hope, quality of life, and self-efficacy among mothers with special needs children. *Inspira Indonesian Journal of Psychological Research*, 3(1), 1-7.
- Sharifi, M., Movallali, G., Younesi, S. J., Rostami, M., & Biglarian, A. (2015). The effectiveness of mental rehabilitation based on hope intervention on increasing hope of students with physical-motor disabilities. *J. Soc. Sci*, 1(4), 1-7.
- Snyder, C. R., Lehman, K. A., Kluck, B., & Monsson, Y. (2006). Hope for rehabilitation and vice versa. *Rehabilitation psychology*, 51(2), 89.
- Snyder, C. R. (2002). Hope theory: Rainbows in the mind. *Psychological inquiry*, 13(4), 249-275.
- Veck, W. (2014). Hope, disability and inclusive participation in education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 18(2), 177-195.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Global education monitoring report: Inclusion and education – All means all*. UNESCO Publishing. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373718>

World Bank. (2022). *Disability inclusion and accountability framework*. World Bank Group.
<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports>